

Synthesis and Plant Growth Retardant Activity of Trialkylammonium Iodides containing an Aromatic Ether Moiety

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N,N-Diethylamines (5, 6) are prepared by treating the phenols (1, 2) with ethylene bromide in the presence of sodium hydroxide, followed by the reaction of the resulting phenoxy bromides (3, 4) with diethylamine and potassium carbonate in acetone. *N,N*-Dimethylamines (20-22) are prepared by treating the phenoxyethanoic acids (11-13) with thionyl chloride and then treating the resulting acid chlorides (14-16) with aqueous dimethylamine to get the amides (17-19) followed by LAH reduction. These tertiary amines are converted to quaternary salts of ammonia by treating them with methyl and ethyl iodides and are tested as plant growth retardants on seeds of turnip (*Brassica rapa*, Var. L₁).

In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and plant growth retardant activity of some quaternary salts of ammonia containing an aromatic moiety^{1,2}, the present work was undertaken to prepare ten new quaternary salts of ammonia having aromatic ether moiety and tested them as plant growth retardants on turnip seeds (*Brassica rapa*, Var. L₁).

Phenol (1/2) was treated with ethylene bromide³ in the presence of aqueous NaOH solution to give 2-phenoxybromoethane (3), which when refluxed with diethylamine and K₂CO₃ in acetone⁴ produced *N,N*-diethyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (5). Its pmr spectrum gave a triplet at δ 1.0 (N(CH₂CH₃)₂), a multiplet at 2.5-3.0 (-CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂) and a triplet at 4.0 (OCH₂CH₃). *N,N*-Diethyl-2-(4-methoxyphenoxy)aminoethane (6) was prepared from *p*-methoxyphenol (2) following the above procedure (Chart 1).

Chart 1

Phenoxyethanoic acid (11) was converted into its acid chloride (14) by treating with thionyl chloride for 16 h at room temperature⁵, which when treated with 38% aqueous solution of dimethylamine at low temperature⁶ gave *N,N*-dimethyl-2-phenoxyethanamide (17) in quantitative yield. Its ir spectrum gave a prominent peak at 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide) and pmr spectrum depicts peaks at δ 3.02, 3.15 (3H, each s, CON(CH₃)₂) and 4.72 (2H, s, Ar-O-CH₂). The amide (17) was then reduced with LAH in dry ether⁶ to get *N,N*-dimethyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (20). Its ir spectrum showed no peak at 1660 cm⁻¹ and pmr spectrum depicts peak at δ 2.15 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 2.8 (2H, t, CH₂-N(CH₃)₂) and 4.45 (2H, t, OCH₂CH). Following the above procedure, 2-methyl-2-phenoxyethanoic acid (12) prepared by

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS (mg dm⁻³) OF QUATERNARY SALTS OF AMMONIA ON TURNIP (*Brassica rapa*) SEED GERMINATION*

Compd. no.	Percentage germination				Length of seedling (in cm) (Average, 50 seeds)			
	10	25	50	100	10	25	50	100
7	84.84	82.85	52.94	12.5	1.564	0.853	0.774	0.475
8	82.35	36.66	6.25	0	1.202	0.780	0.450	0
9	86.1	69.96	56.66	6.25	2.064	1.230	0.970	0
10	86.1	72.72	39.39	9.67	1.510	1.220	0.952	0.666
23	93.3	82.35	39.39	7.0 ¹	1.642	1.088	0.599	0
25	78.12	12.12	6.25	0	1.500	1.300	0.400	0
26	91.66	69.69	15.15	3.33	1.296	1.173	0.720	0.20
27	90.90	85.29	48.48	11.76	1.563	1.096	0.806	0.375
28	81.81	88.23	38.88	12.90	1.339	1.296	1.164	0.175
ABA at 5 ppm	12.12				0.425			
Water (control)	100				1.7622			

*Data after 48 h.

heating the phenol with α -bromopropanoic acid and sodium hydroxide⁶, and 2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)ethanoic acid (13) by heating *p*-methoxyphenol with chloroacetic acid and sodium hydroxide were converted to *N,N*-dimethyl-2-methyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (21) and *N,N*-dimethyl-2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)aminoethane (22) respectively.

The trialkylamines (5, 6, 20–22) were then treated with methyl iodide and ethyl iodide in dry ether to give the corresponding quaternary ammonium compounds (7–10, 23–28). The compounds were tested on turnip seeds (*B. rapa*, Var. L₁) and percentage germination and average length of seedlings were recorded. All the compounds showed decrease in germination as well as in the length of seedlings when compared with the control experiment in water. The plant growth retarding effect increased with the increase of concentration. When compared with ABA, these compounds showed fairly good plant growth retardant activity.

Experimental

Boiling and melting points are uncorrected. Drying of all organic compounds was done over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ir spectra (film) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 881 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CCl₄) on a Varian EM-390 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel impregnated with CaSO₄ was used for tlc.

N,N-Diethyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (5): To a mixture of phenol (1; 2.6 g) and ethylene bromide (6.7 g), a solution of sodium hydroxide (1 g in 10 ml of water) was added dropwise over a period of 1 h, and then refluxed with stirring for 6 h at 120°. The cooled reaction mixture was washed with 2*N* NaOH and dried. Removal of the solvent gave the bromide (3; 2.4 g, 42.6%).

A mixture of 2-phenoxybromoethane (3; 2.4 g), diethylamine (1 g) and K₂CO₃ (1.5 g) was stirred and refluxed with acetone at 60° for 6 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and most of the acetone

was removed by distillation. Water (15 ml) was then added and the solution was extracted with ether. After drying the ether extract, the solvent was vacuum-distilled to give the amine (5; 1.3 g, 56.5%), b.p. 135–08°/8–10 mm (Found: C, 74.52; H, 9.93; N, 7.14. C₁₂H₁₉ON requires: C, 74.6; H, 9.84; N, 7.25%); ν_{\max} 3 050, 2 975, 2 820, 1 600, 1 500, 1 460, 1 390, 1 300, 1 250, 1 180, 1 080, 1 040, 885, 760 and 700 cm⁻¹; δ 1.0 (6H, t, *J* 8 Hz, N(CH₂-CH₃)), 2.5–3.0 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 4.0 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz, OCH₂CH₂) and 6.9–7.3 (5H, m, ArH).

N,N-Diethyl-2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)aminoethane(6): It was prepared as described above first by converting methoxy phenol (6.7 g) into 2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)bromoethane (4; 56.4%) and then reacting bromide (4; 6.2 g) with diethylamine (2.2 g) and potassium carbonate (3.3 g) in 58% yield, b.p. 95–97°/6–8 mm (Found: C, 69.73; H, 9.91; N, 6.17. C₁₃H₂₂O₂N requires: C, 69.64; H, 9.82; N, 6.25%); ν_{\max} 3 050, 2 960, 2 870, 1 600w, 1 515, 1 465, 1 385, 1 300, 1 235, 1 185, 1 115, 1 040, 940, 825 and 740 cm⁻¹; δ 1.1 (6H, t, *J* 8 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)), 2.4–2.8 (6H, m, CH₂-N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.9 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 4.75 (3H, s, ArOCH₃) and 6.97 (4H, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-phenoxyethanamide (17): A mixture of phenoxyacetic acid (11; 2 g) and thionyl chloride (4.5 ml) was kept at room temperature for 16 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed, and the residue distilled to yield the acid chloride (14; 5.5 g) as a colourless liquid.

The acid chloride (14; 5.5 g) without further purification was dissolved in dry benzene (40 ml) and added dropwise with stirring to an ice-cold solution of dimethylamine (38% solution in water; 40 ml). Stirring was continued for another 4 h and the mixture left at room temperature overnight. The benzene layer was then separated after diluting with water (100 ml) and the aqueous part further extracted with benzene (5 × 50 ml). The combined organic extract was washed with 10% aqueous KOH (25 ml) followed by water, dried and the solvent removed.

The residue was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the solid amide (**17**; 3.2 g, 56%), m.p. 124–25° (Found: C, 67.14; H, 7.21; N, 7.91. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2N$ requires: C, 67.03, H, 7.25; N, 7.82%); ν_{max} 3 040, 2 950, 2 880, 1 665, 1 600, 1 500, 1 460, 1 415, 1 405, 1 360, 1 315, 1 300, 1 240, 1 180, 1 070, 1 020, 845, 820, 760 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 3.02 and 3.15 (3H, each s, $-CON(CH_3)_2$), 4.72 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.95–7.6 (5H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-methyl-2-phenoxyethanamide (**18**): 2-Methyl-2-phenoxyethanoic acid (**12**; 4.4 g) was first treated with thionyl chloride (9.1 ml) and then the resulting acid chloride (**15**; 5 g) was reacted with dimethylamine (36.4 ml; 38% solution in water) as described above to give the amide (**18**; 3 g, 57%), m.p. 64–65° (Found: C, 68.45; H, 7.69; N, 7.31. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$ requires: C, 68.39; H, 7.77; N, 7.25%); ν_{max} 3 050, 2 960, 2 940, 2 850, 1 660, 1 600, 1 460, 1 380, 1 305, 1 240, 1 160, 1 100, 1 040, 960, 800, 760, 720 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.63 (3H, d, J 9 Hz, $OCH(CH_3)$), 3.0, 3.13 (3H, each s, $CON(CH_3)_2$), 5.2 (1H, q, J 9 Hz, $OCH(CH_3)$) and 6.93–7.5 (5H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)ethanamide (**19**): *p*-Methoxyphenol (**2**; 8 g) and chloroacetic acid (6.0 g) were melted together on a water-bath. Aqueous sodium hydroxide (6*N*; 25 ml) was then added to it slowly with stirring and the reaction mixture heated on a water-bath for 3 h with occasional shaking. It was then diluted with cold water and acidified with concentrated HCl and the resulting light brown solid was washed and dried (**13**; 4.5 g, 39%).

The acid (**13**; 4.5 g) was first treated with thionyl chloride (9 ml) and the resulting acid chloride (**16**; 4.2 g) was then treated with aqueous methylamine (38%; 20 ml) to furnish the amide (**19**; 3.5 g, 80%) as described in the preparation of **17** (Found: C, 62.80; H, 7.51; N, 6.69. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3N$ requires: C, 62.85; H, 7.6; N, 6.61%); ν_{max} 3 045, 2 955, 2 840, 1 680, 1 600, 1 510, 1 460, 1 405, 1 360, 1 300, 1 225, 1 195, 1 160, 1 120, 1 080, 1 040, 830, 805, 785, 745 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 3.0, 3.3 (3H, each s, $N(CH_3)_2$), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH_2), 4.55 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$) and 6.90 (4H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (**20**): *N,N*-Dimethylamide (**17**; 1.5 g) in dry ether (50 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred slurry of LAH (1.0 g) in dry ether (100 ml) at room temperature. After stirring for 16 h, the mixture was cooled and treated successively with water (1.3 ml), 15% aqueous NaOH (1.3 ml) and water (3.9 ml) and stirred further for 15 min. The resulting granular solid was washed with ether and the combined extract was dried. Removal of the solvent followed by the distillation of the residue gave the amine (**20**; 1 g, 69%), b.p. 105–07°/8–10 mm (Found: C, 72.63; H, 9.0; N, 8.54. $C_{10}H_{15}ON$ requires: C, 72.72; H, 9.09; N, 8.48%); ν_{max} 3 055, 2 950, 2 880, 1 600, 1 500, 1 475, 1 420, 1 405, 1 360, 1 315, 1 295, 1 240, 1 180, 1 160,

1 075, 1 015, 840, 790, 760 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.15 (6H, s, $-N(CH_3)_2$), 2.8 (2H, t, $CH_2-N(CH_3)_2$), 4.45 (2H, t, OCH_2CH_2) and 6.9–7.6 (5H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-methyl-2-phenoxyaminoethane (**21**): *N,N*-Dimethylamide (**18**; 2 g) in dry ether (50 ml) was reduced with LAH (1.2 g) as described above to give the tertiary amine (**21**; 1 g, 54%), m.p. 68° (Found: C, 73.80; H, 9.54; N, 7.91. $C_{11}H_{17}ON$ requires: C, 73.74; H, 9.49; N, 7.82%); ν_{max} 3 070, 2 930, 2 875, 1 605, 1 500, 1 460, 1 400, 1 380, 1 355, 1 305, 1 295, 1 245, 1 185, 1 120, 1 100, 1 040, 960, 935, 890, 805, 755, 740 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.4 (3H, d, J 8.5 Hz, $OCH(CH_3)$), 2.20 (6H, s, $CH_2N(CH_3)_2$), 2.83 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, $CH(CH_3)CH_2N$), 4.8 (1H, m, $OCH(CH_3)CH_2$) and 6.8–7.4 (5H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(4'-methoxyphenoxy)aminoethane (**22**): *N,N*-Dimethylamide (**19**; 3.5 g) in dry ether (80 ml) was reduced with LAH (1.9 g) as described in the preparation of **20** to give the tertiary amine (**22**; 1.8 g, 55%), b.p. 102–05°/5–7 mm (Found: C, 62.80; H, 7.69; N, 6.51. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2N$ requires: C, 62.85; H, 7.6; N, 6.6%); ν_{max} 3 050, 2 970, 2 840, 1 600, 1 505, 1 460, 1 440, 1 420, 1 400, 1 350, 1 230, 1 180, 1 160, 1 105, 1 075, 1 035, 825, 800, 740 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.1 (6H, s, $N(CH_3)_2$), 2.95 (2H, t, $CH_2N(CH_3)_2$), 4.5 (2H, t, OCH_2CH_2), 4.7 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$) and 6.97 (4H, ArH).

N,N,N-Trimethyl-2-methyl-2-phenoxyethylammonium iodide (**25**): To a solution of dimethylamine (**21**; 0.5 g) in dry ether (10 ml), was added methyl iodide (1 ml) and the mixture stirred for 2 h and then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The resulting yellow coloured solid was filtered to give quaternary ammonium iodide (**25**; 800 mg, 90%), m.p. 73° (Found: C, 44.79; H, 6.30; N, 4.30. $C_{12}H_{20}ONI$ requires: C, 44.85; H, 6.23; N, 4.36%).

Following the above procedure the quaternary salts of ammonia (**7–10, 23, 24, 26–28**) from the trialkylamines (**5, 6, 20–22**) were prepared by taking each amine (0.5 g) in dry ether (10 ml) and treating it with methyl or ethyl iodide (1 ml); yield 78–92%. The m.p.s. of compounds **9, 10, 24** and **26** were found to be 110, 95, 105 and 70° respectively, and gave satisfactory elemental analysis. All other compounds were either hygroscopic in nature or thick oil.

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